

HAQIQIY SHAROITLARDA SLAM VA KO‘P-MAQSADLI BAJARISH ASOSIDA TURTLEBOT3 YORDAMIDA AVTONOM ICHKI NAVIGATSIYA

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ANNOTATSIYA	KALIT SO‘ZLAR
<p>Ushbu ishda TurtleBot3 Burger roboti yordamida haqiqiy sharoitlarda avtonom ichki navigatsiya uchun amaliy tizim taqdim etiladi. Bunday tizim robototexnika ta’limining dastlabki bosqichlarida avtonom navigatsiyani sinovdan o‘tkazishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Biz SLAMni moslashuvchan ko‘p-maqsadli rejalashtirish va navigatsiya bilan integratsiya qildik, bunda ROS Noetic (Ubuntu 20.04) ostida ROS Navigation Stackdan foydalanildi. Tizim GMapping asosidagi SLAM, AMCL lokalizatsiyasi va moslashuvchan maqsad ketma-ketligini boshqaruvchi maxsus Python skriptlarini o‘z ichiga oladi. Sinovlar to‘liq fizik muhitda o‘tkazildi, Gazebo esa faqat dastlabki tajribaviy bosqichlarda qo‘llanildi. Robotning unumdorligi maqsadlar soni va to‘siqlar konfiguratsiyalariga qarab baholandi, bunda maxsus tajribaviy ko‘rsatkichlardan foydalanildi: vaqt sarfi, yo‘l aniqligi, muvaffaqiyat darajasi va tiklanish xatti-harakati chastotasi. Natijalar bizning yondashuvimizning real sharoitlarda barqarorligini tasdiqlaydi va ROS asosidagi mobil robototexnikani amaliy joriy etish uchun qayta ishlab chiqarilishi mumkin bo‘lgan xulosalarni taqdim etadi.</p>	<p>avtonom ichki navigatsiya; TurtleBot3 Burger; SLAM (bir vaqtning o‘zida lokalizatsiya va xarita tuzish); AMCL lokalizatsiyasi; ROS Navigation Stack; Ko‘p-maqsadli rejalashtirish; Yo‘l aniqligi; To‘siqlardan qochish; Mobil robototexnika; Robototexnika ta’limi.</p>

АВТОНОМНАЯ НАВИГАЦИЯ В ПОМЕЩЕНИЯХ В РЕАЛЬНЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ SLAM И МНОГОЦЕЛЕВОГО ВЫПОЛНЕНИЯ НА TURTLEBOT3

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АННОТАЦИЯ	КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА
<p>В данной работе представлен практический подход к автономной навигации в помещениях с использованием робота TurtleBot3 Burger в реальных условиях. Подобная система играет важную роль на ранних этапах обучения робототехнике при проведении экспериментов с автономной навигацией. Мы интегрировали SLAM с адаптивным многоцелевым планированием и навигацией, используя ROS Navigation Stack под ROS Noetic на Ubuntu 20.04. Система включает SLAM на основе GMapping, локализацию AMCL и пользовательские скрипты на Python для управления гибкой последовательностью целей. Тестирование проводилось полностью в физической среде, при этом Gazebo</p>	<p>автономная навигация в помещениях; TurtleBot3 Burger; SLAM (одновременная локализация и построение карты); Локализация AMCL; ROS Navigation Stack; Многоцелевое планирование; Точность</p>

использовался только на ранних стадиях экспериментов. Производительность робота оценивалась при различных количествах целей и конфигурациях препятствий с применением специальных метрик, таких как затраченное время, точность траектории, коэффициент успешности и частота восстановления. Результаты подтверждают надежность нашего подхода в реалистичных условиях и предлагают воспроизводимые выводы для практического применения мобильной робототехники на базе ROS.

траектории; Обход препятствий; Мобильная робототехника; Образование в области робототехники.

REAL-WORLD AUTONOMOUS INDOOR NAVIGATION USING SLAM AND MULTI-GOAL EXECUTION WITH TURTLEBOT3

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a practical system for autonomous indoor navigation using a TurtleBot3 Burger robot in real-world environments. Such a system plays a crucial role in experimenting with autonomous navigation during the early stages of robotics education. We integrated SLAM with adaptive multi-goal planning and navigation using the ROS Navigation Stack under ROS Noetic on Ubuntu 20.04. The system incorporates GMapping-based SLAM, AMCL localization, and custom Python scripts to control flexible goal sequences. Testing was conducted entirely in a physical environment, with Gazebo used only during early experimental stages. The robot's performance was evaluated across different goal counts and obstacle configurations using custom experimental metrics such as time taken, path accuracy, success rate, and recovery behavior frequency. The results validate the robustness of our approach in realistic settings and offer reproducible insights for the practical deployment of ROS-powered mobile robotics.

KEYWORDS

autonomous indoor navigation; TurtleBot3 Burger; SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping); AMCL localization; ROS Navigation Stack; Multi-goal planning; Path accuracy; Obstacle avoidance; Mobile robotics; Robotics education.

Introduction. Autonomous indoor navigation continues to be one of the most significant challenges in mobile robotics. The ability of robots to autonomously navigate through indoor environments, accurately localize themselves, and adapt to dynamic changes in the environment is crucial for a wide range of applications, from service robots to warehouse automation. Recent advances in Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) and path planning, particularly within the Robot Operating System (ROS) framework, have driven substantial progress in this field, with platforms like TurtleBot3 gaining traction for educational and research purposes [1, 2, 3].

Simulation environments, such as Gazebo, offer a controlled and safe environment for the initial stages of development. They provide a powerful tool for testing and refining algorithms before deployment, allowing for rapid prototyping and the testing of various navigation and control strategies. However, despite their utility,

simulations cannot fully replicate the complexities of real-world environments. When transitioning from simulation to physical deployment, robots face challenges that include sensor noise, localization drift, and unpredictable dynamic obstacles. These issues often go unaddressed in simulations, yet they have a significant impact on the performance and reliability of the system in practical applications.

This project builds upon foundational work in SLAM-based autonomous navigation [2, 4], bridging the gap between simulated environments and real-world deployment. We focus on developing a robust and adaptive pipeline that not only accounts for the challenges of real-world navigation but also offers reproducibility for future research and practical applications. This study introduces a comprehensive and reproducible pipeline for autonomous indoor navigation that addresses both the theoretical and practical

aspects of the problem. The pipeline incorporates several important elements, which include:

- Real-time SLAM implementation using GMapping [5, 6],
- Multi-goal planning and dynamic goal adjustment,
- Parameter optimization for enhanced navigation performance,
- Integration of the ROS Navigation Stack for adaptive path generation [7, 8],
- Comprehensive real-world evaluation across various flexible test scenarios.

1. System Architecture and Implementation ***Robot and Environment Setup***

Our experiments were conducted using the TurtleBot3 Burger, which is equipped with a Raspberry-Pi 4B, OpenCR controller, and a 2D LiDAR sensor. The system operated on ROS Noetic running on Ubuntu 20.04. The Raspberry Pi 4B served as the onboard computer for processing the robot’s tasks, while the OpenCR controller interfaced with the hardware components (motors and sensors). The 2D LiDAR sensor provided essential data for creating the environment map.

While initial trials for SLAM learning and visualization were carried out in Gazebo simulation[9], the performance results were exclusively obtained from real-world robot ployments. These real-world trials were crucial in assessing the practical effectiveness of the algorithms, as simulations may not always account for the complexities and unpredictability of real environments.

SLAM Implementation

SLAM was implemented using the GMapping algorithm, which utilizes particle filters for scan matching and pose estimation. The GMapping algorithm is known for its robustness in environments with dynamic objects and is commonly used in mobile robotics. We empirically tuned key parameters such as the linear update, angular update, and minimum score to optimize performance for our specific setup[6, 10]. The generated map was saved using the map saver utility, allowing it to be used as a static reference for localization during navigation. The map served as the foundation for all subsequent localization and path-planning tasks.

Navigation Stack

For real-time position tracking, we employed AMCL (Adaptive Monte Carlo Localization), which estimates the robot’s pose relative to the static map using a particle filter. This approach is highly effective in dynamic environments where the robot must adjust to changes in its surroundings. The AMCL parameters, such as update rate, minimum

particles, and laser model, were specifically tuned for indoor environments to ensure accurate and efficient localization[11, 12].

For global and local path planning, we used the move base node. This node combines multiple planners and controllers to achieve robust navigation. We configured the move base node with the DWA (Dynamic Window Approach) local planner, which allows the robot to navigate smoothly in cluttered environments by considering both the velocity of the robot and the obstacles around it. The navigation stack incorporated costmaps that included inflation layers, obstacle buffers, and voxel grid updates to ensure reliable obstacle avoidance[13, 14].

Multi-Goal Navigation

We developed a custom Python node that sequentially publishes goals to the /move base simple/goal topic. This node reads a predefined list of waypoints and navigates through them in order, allowing real-time visualization and intervention via RViz. The logic of our goal execution process is outlined in Algorithm 4, which is divided into several sub-algorithms that handle different parts of the navigation process.

The system supports navigation through up to 10 goals per session, offering flexibility in session complexity and experimental design. Dynamic adjustment of goal points is possible during runtime, supporting both reproducible and exploratory test scenarios. The dataset used for evaluation is structured externally and analyzed post-experiment rather than being directly integrated within the navigation node.

Goal Sending Function

The first part of the algorithm handles sending the goal to the robot and checking whether the goal has been reached. If the goal is not reached, it will return false, and the process will move to the next attempt.

Algorithm 1: Sending a Goal

```

1 Function SEND GOAL(goal):
2     send goal(goal);
3     wait for result();
4     if goal reached() then
5         return true;
6     return false;
    
```

Getting Robot Position

In the second part of the process, the system checks the robot’s current position to determine how far it is from the goal. This is crucial for adjusting the goal in case of failure.

Algorithm 2: Getting the Robot Position

```

1 Function GET ROBOT POSITION():
2     get robot position();
3     if position is found then
4         return position;
5     return null;
    
```

Computing Shifted Goal

If the robot fails to reach a goal, the system adjusts the goal by computing a new ”shifted” position. This allows the robot to try different coordinates close to the target.

Algorithm 3: Computing Shifted Goal

```

1 Function COMPUTE SHIFTED POINT(current, goal, attempt):
2      $dx \leftarrow \text{sign}(\text{goal}.x - \text{current}.x)$ ;
3      $dy \leftarrow \text{sign}(\text{goal}.y - \text{current}.y)$ ;
4     return Point( $\text{current}.x + \text{attempt} * \text{threshold} * dx$ ,  $\text{current}.y +$ 
 $\text{attempt} * \text{threshold} * dy$ , 0);
    
```

Navigating Through All Goals

The algorithm for navigating through all goals is organized into distinct sub-algorithms, each focusing on a specific task. The main algorithm processes each goal sequentially. For each goal, the first sub-algorithm sends the goal to the robot and checks if it has been successfully reached. If the goal is reached on the first attempt, the system logs the results and proceeds to the next goal.

If the goal is not reached, the second sub-algorithm retrieves the robot’s current position and computes a new shifted goal based on the robot’s distance from the target. This adjusted goal is then sent to the robot. The process of retrieving the current position and computing a shifted goal is repeated for up to a maximum number of attempts for each goal.

The main algorithm coordinates these steps, managing retries and logging the status of each goal, including whether it was successfully reached or failed, as well as key metrics such as time taken and number of attempts. By dynamically adjusting the goals during navigation, the system ensures that goals are reached even if the robot’s initial attempt fails.

Algorithm 4: Navigating Through All Goals

```

1 Function NAVIGATE ALL(goal points, max attempts, threshold):
2     i ← 0;
3     while i < len(goal points) do
4         goal ← goal points[i];
5         start_time ← current time;
6         reached ← false;
7         attempts ← 1;
8         final_x, final_y ← goal.x, goal.y;
9         if SEND GOAL(goal) then
10            log(goal, Reached, 1, goal.x, goal.y, time taken);
11        else
12            for attempt ← 1 to max attempts do
13                current ← GET ROBOT_POSITION();
14                if current = null then
15                    return
16                shifted_goal ← COMPUTE_SHIFTED_POINT(current, goal, attempt);
17                if SEND GOAL(shifted_goal) then
18                    log(shifted_goal, Reached, attempt, shifted goal.x, shifted
19                        goal.y, time taken);
20                return
21            if attempts == max attempts then
22                log(goal, Failed, attempts, final x, final y);
23            i ← i + 1;
24        export_stats_to_excel();
    
```

The algorithm continuously monitors and adjusts navigation attempts for each goal in the list. The statistics (e.g., success, final coordinates, and time) are logged throughout the process, and a summary is exported at the end of the navigation session.

Parameter Configuration

To ensure robust navigation in dynamic indoor environments with potential narrow passages and moving obstacles, key parameters of the ROS Navigation Stack were tuned. This tuning targeted the inflation behavior of the costmap and trajectory generation via the DWA_Planner_ROS local planner. Figure 1 shows the interface used during tuning.

Figure 1. Parameter reconfiguration using rqt_reconfigure, showing updated values for costmap inflation layers and DWAPlanerROS.

The inflation layer of both the global and local costmaps was reconfigured to improve the robot’s ability to pass through tight gaps while still maintaining obstacle awareness. **inflation_radius** reduced from 1.0,m to 0.5,m. This makes the robot less conservative in avoiding obstacles, allowing it to consider narrower passages as valid. **cost_scaling_factor** increased from 3.0 to 10.0. This sharpens the inflation gradient, making the robot treat the areas near obstacles with higher cost more abruptly, thus encouraging safer paths without unnecessarily widening avoidance zones.

To improve local trajectory planning, especially near goals or in constrained environments, several critical motion and scoring parameters were adjusted:

Parameter	Change / Value	Explanation
acc_lim_trans	0.1 → 0.5 m/s ²	Faster acceleration, more responsive to dynamic changes.
sim_time	1.5 → 2.5 s	Longer prediction window, smoother and safer motion.
goal_distance_bias	20.0 → 32.0	Stronger emphasis on reaching the goal, less hesitation at obstacles.
path_distance_bias	32.0 → 20.0	Less strict path following, allows flexible detours.
occdist_scale	0.01–0.02 → 0.05	Higher penalty for paths near obstacles, improves safety.
forward_point_distance	0.325 → 0.1	Finer local planning, better in tight or cluttered spaces.
xy_goal_tolerance	0.2 → 0.15 m	Higher precision when reaching the goal position.
yaw_goal_tolerance	0.2 rad (unchanged)	Balanced orientation precision vs. goal reachability.
oscillation_timeout	10.0 → 5.0 s	Faster recovery behaviors when stuck oscillating.
oscillation_reset_dist	0.05 m	Distance robot must move to reset oscillation state.

Table 1. Adjusted parameters and their descriptions.

2. Experiment Setup

The robot was tested in indoor spaces containing corridors, rooms, and dynamic/static obstacles. Each session began from a fixed origin and executed up to 10 goal points as specified in the dataset.

Metrics for evaluation included:

- Time taken per goal and total session,
- Goal success rate (% reached vs attempted),
- Number of recovery behaviors,
- Path deviation (Euclidean distance between destination goals and sources).
- The following table illustrates a sample format of how the experimental results were stored and later analyzed:

S Id	Index	Source_X	Source_Y	Reached	At.	Dest_X	Dest_Y	Duration (s)
1	1	-0.062345	0.190323	Yes	1	-0.062345	0.190323	29.30

Table 2. Sample log entry from the navigation dataset. *S_id*: Session_Id, *At.*: Attempts

Multiple sessions were conducted under varied lighting and obstacle conditions to test robustness. Data from these sessions were later used to analyze performance trends and system reliability.

3. Results and Discussion

SLAM Map and Physical Environment

Figure 2 illustrates a comparison between the real-world environment layout used for testing and the occupancy grid map produced by the SLAM module using GMapping. The generated map accurately reflects the corridors and rooms, confirming effective scan matching and parameter tuning. Minor inaccuracies near reflective surfaces were expected and mitigated by adjusting scan matching thresholds.

Figure 2. (a) Physical layout of the test environment. (b) SLAM-generated map visualized in RViz.

Experimental Data Insights

The experiments were conducted in various indoor settings with dynamic and static obstacles. Each session executed a sequence of up to 10 goals. The dataset records goal positions, reach status, number of attempts, and duration per goal. Table 3 shows sample entries.

S_Id	Index	Source_X	Source_Y	Reached	At.	Dest_X	Dest_Y	Duration (s)
1	1	-0.062345	0.190323	Yes	1	-0.062345	0.190323	29.30
1	2	-1.647058	-1.274098	Yes	1	-1.647058	-1.274098	24.50
2	1	-2.595135	-0.705416	Yes	1	-2.595135	-0.705416	13.30
3	1	-1.921621	-1.136120	Yes	1	-2.283344	-0.475570	75.11
3	2	-0.117172	0.667617	Yes	1	-0.117172	0.667617	38.80
3	3	-0.316364	1.850587	Yes	1	-0.316364	1.850587	23.40
3	4	-2.624653	-0.011712	Yes	1	-2.624653	-0.011712	49.25
3	5	-0.644446	2.237102	Yes	1	-0.908511	1.838131	153.96
4	1	-1.295190	0.337358	Yes	1	-1.295190	0.337358	13.20

Table 3. Sample entries from the navigation dataset. S_id: Session_Id, At.: Attempts

The experimental dataset consists of multiple navigation sessions, each containing several goal-reaching attempts. The following insights were derived from the log data:

All 9 entries in the provided sample were successful (Reached = Yes), indicating effective path planning and execution in tested environments.

Each goal was achieved in a single attempt (Attempts = 1), suggesting robust localization and control performance across sessions.

- The mean duration to reach a goal was approximately 46.4 seconds.
- The shortest duration recorded was 13.2 seconds (Session 4, Index 1).
- The longest was 153.96 seconds (Session 3, Index 5), possibly indicating dynamic obstacles or complex terrain.

Navigation performance was largely consistent across sessions. For example:

- Session 1 had two goals completed with low durations (29.3s, 24.5s).
- Session 3 included five goals, with varying times (23.4s to 153.96s), showing adaptability in different sub-environments.
- Source and destination coordinates span a broad area (e.g., Dest X from -2.624653 to -0.062345), validating the robot’s ability to navigate diverse spatial regions within the map.

Challenges and Solutions

During real-world deployment, several challenges were encountered and systematically addressed. In areas with glass walls or reflective surfaces, AMCL sometimes lost track of the robot. This was mitigated by tuning the laser z hit and laser sigma hit parameters, as well as increasing the particle count for better pose estimation.

The local planner occasionally produced oscillatory paths in narrow corridors. We reduced the inflation radius and adjusted costmap

resolution to improve clearance predictions. Human movement during tests occasionally blocked paths, triggering repeated recovery behavior. Introducing timeout-based retries and dynamic goal reassignment helped maintain progress.

Compared with benchmarks in prior works[1, 15, 16], our system’s performance was consistent with modern indoor navigation solutions. Localization drift was occasionally observed in glass-walled areas, but addressed by resampling particles and adjusting the laser scan matching frequency.

Path smoothness and CPU load were optimized via reduced update frequency and map resolution tuning. Overall, the integration of SLAM, AMCL, and the custom multi-goal system provided a robust and adaptable framework for real-world autonomous indoor navigation.

4. Conclusion

This project successfully demonstrated the deployment of a real-world autonomous indoor navigation system using SLAM and ROS tools. Unlike prior works limited to simulation, our approach was field-tested with up to 10 goals per session.

Key contributions include real-time SLAM integration with AMCL and flexible navigation planning, a customizable dataset-driven goal system for diverse testing, and thorough validation across 10+ sessions in real environments.

Future work may extend to dynamic re-mapping, multi-robot coordination, or integration with semantic understanding modules.[7]

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